

Removal of chromium(III), iron(III) and nickel(II) by synthetic analogue of mica mineral sodium potassium fluorophlogopite

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Abstract : The efficient removal of the metal ions chromium(III), iron(III) and nickel(II) from industrial effluent using synthetic analogue of the mica mineral sodium potassium fluorophlogopite has been studied. Sorption of metal ions from aqueous waste by the synthetic analogue SPFP has been studied as a function of contact time between aqueous and solid phase, temperature, weight of sorbent, pH of the solution and metal ion concentration. These factors have remarkable effect on sorption process. To characterize the synthesized material, XRPD, EDS, FT-IR and TGA techniques are used. This synthesized material shows good sorption capacity for Fe^{III} in comparison to Cr^{III} and Ni^{II}. The concentration of metal ions, temperature and weight of sorbent also has pronounced effect on over all sorptivity of the material.

Keywords : Sorption, metal ions, waste water.

In recent years growth of industries has led to introduction of pollutants in nature, especially the heavy metal ions like Cr^{III}, Fe^{III} and Ni^{II} usually present in industrial waste water. Heavy metals containing waste is generated from industries like metallurgical, mining, chemical, leather, distilleries, sugar, battery, electroplating and pigments¹. Chromium is found in natural water in two oxidation states Cr^{III} and Cr^{VI}. The former is essential element in mammals whereas the later is reported to be toxic. According to World Health Organization (WHO) standard permissible limits for these metal ions viz. Cr^{III}, Fe^{III} and Ni^{II} is 0.005, 1.0 and 0.5 ppm respectively². However, in industrial waste water these values approach to hundreds of ppm. Various methods such as solvent extraction, solid-liquid extraction, electro-dialysis, oxidation, ultra-filtration and ion exchange have been employed for purification purpose³.

In this context, the present work deals with removal of Cr^{III}, Fe^{III} and Ni^{II} by the synthetic analogue of mica mineral sodium potassium fluorophlogopite [SPFP] from industrial waste water. Effect of contact time, variation in aqueous phase to sorbent ratio, effect of temperature and concentration of metal ions on sorption of Cr^{III}, Fe^{III} and Ni^{II} by the synthetic gel SPFP has been investigated. Characterization of synthetic gel has been carried out by X-ray powder diffraction (XRPD), energy dispersive spectrometry (EDS), FT-IR and thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) techniques.

Experimental

Analogue of the mica mineral SPFP has been synthesized by hydrothermal method using teflon lined stainless steel autoclave at 200 °C for 72 h. X-Ray powder diffraction pattern

of the synthetic gel has been recorded using Cu-K α radiation in the range $2\theta = 10^\circ$ to 90° at a scanning speed of 1s/step. The chemical composition of the synthesized gel was checked by elemental analysis of ions Na, K, Mg, Al and Si using energy dispersive spectroscopy. To confirm the presence of -OH group and the metal-oxygen group, FT-IR analysis was carried out using NICOLET-410 spectrometer. The exact number of water molecules bound to the gel was ascertained by thermogravimetric analysis using Netzsch thermobalance, STA-409. In order to establish the exchangeable ions in SPFP, which are likely to be exchanged during the sorption process, ICP-AES analysis was made. Sorption experiments have been performed at 25 ± 1.0 °C using thermostated water bath. Sorption of Cr^{III}, Fe^{III} and Ni^{II} on SPFP gel has been carried out using batch technique. To make Cr^{III}, Fe^{III} and Ni^{II} solutions at pH 7.0, 7.0 and 10.0 respectively, chromium(III) chloride 5-hydrate, ferric chloride anhydrous and nickel(II) chloride 6-hydrate compounds, respectively has been used and no complex forming agent was used to keep the ions in solution phase. In most of the experiments (except when aqueous phase : SPFP ratio was varied) aqueous phase to SPFP ratio was fixed as 1 : 4 by taking 100 mg of SPFP and 25 ml of the aqueous phase containing one of the metal ions.

The following parameters were changed : contact time between the two phase; weight of sorbent; pH of the solution and metal ion concentration. The chemicals and reagents used were of analytical grade.

All the sorption experiments have been carried out in duplicate and care has been taken to centrifuge the solution repeatedly to avoid any solid particles in the aqueous phase.

The distribution of Cr^{III} , Fe^{III} and Ni^{II} on SPFP is expressed in terms of distribution coefficient K_d which is determined by

$$K_d = \frac{C - C'}{C'} \times \frac{V}{w} \quad \text{ml/g}$$

where C and C' are the initial concentration and concentration after equilibration of Cr^{III} , Fe^{III} and Ni^{II} respectively. V is the volume of solution in milliliters and w is weight of exchanger (SPFP) in grams. The quantitative estimation of initial and final concentration of metal ions in the aqueous phase before and after sorption experiments is made by using spectrophotometric methods. Cr^{III} , Fe^{III} and Ni^{II} was estimated by using 1,5-diphenyl carbazide, thiocyanate and dimethyl glyoxime respectively. Cr^{III} ions react with 1,5-diphenyl carbazide, Fe^{III} ions react with thiocyanate and Ni^{II} reacts with dimethyl glyoxime to form a violet, red and pink colour complex which is soluble in water and measured spectrophotometrically at wave lengths 543, 482 and 535 nm.

Table 1. ICP-AES analysis of SPFP gel equilibrated with 0.1 M HNO_3 solution for 3 h

Metal ions	Amount (mg/ml)	
	Blank sample	Sample equilibrated with SPFP
Na	5.00	259.00
K	4.00	444.00
Mg	1.00	1250.00
Al	0.01	0.01

Results and discussion

Material characterization :

The results of X-ray powder diffraction pattern of the sample shows maximum peak intensity at $2\theta = 60.3$ which corresponds to $d = 1.533 \text{ \AA}$. These values are in agreement with the standard reported values and can be assigned the index of (010)⁴. The weight percentage of ions, Na, K, Mg, Al and Si in the synthesized gel SPFP obtained from energy dispersive analysis, agree very well with the weight percentage of these metals taken for synthesis⁴. In an effort to understand the structural characteristics of the short range level, FT-IR (using NICOLET-410 spectrometer) experiments were performed. FT-IR spectrum of the synthesized gel shows absorption band at 1103 cm^{-1} and 957 cm^{-1} , which can be ascribed to the Si-O-Si and Si-O-Al stretching vibration respectively. The Si-O stretching and bending of Si-OH appears at 898 and 957 cm^{-1} ⁵.

The stretching vibration for AlO_4^{2-} are located in the 620 – 900 cm^{-1} region. The peak at 1639 and 1384 cm^{-1} associated with H-O-H bending and 3431 cm^{-1} is associated with -OH stretching of absorbed water. The number of water molecules

bound in the gel was six as ascertained by thermogravimetric analysis. The synthesized hydrothermal phase has a composition $\text{Na}_{0.5}\text{K}_{0.5}\text{Mg}_3(\text{Si}_3\text{AlO}_{10})\text{F}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$. ICP-AES analysis (Table 1) shows that as compared to blank sample the SPFP equilibrated solution showed higher amount of Na, K and Mg. All the three metal ions in SPFP matrix are labile which may get exchanged with the ions viz. Cr^{III} , Fe^{III} and Ni^{II} present in the solution phase. In addition the synthetic analogue also act as sorbent due to the framework structure containing channels and interconnected voids where the molecules or ions may get sorbed. Although the ion exchange process is quantitative but due to the occurrence of simultaneous sorption, the exact quantitative results cannot be made.

The effect of contact time between aqueous phase and sorbent on sorption process was studied at fixed metal ion concentration on 0.01 N and 100 mg sorbent dose. Fig. 1a gives the data on effect of time for the sorption of Cr^{III} , Fe^{III} and Ni^{II} at pH 7.0, 7.0 and 10.0 respectively on the SPFP gel between 1.0 to 24.0 h. The K_d values for all the three metal ions increases with increasing time of equilibration. However in all further experiments time was fixed as three hours because after three hours the K_d values remain more or less constant.

Fig. 1a. Sorption of Cr^{III} , Fe^{III} and Ni^{II} by synthetic analogue of SPFP at varying contact time.

The experiments for the change in aqueous phase to sorbent ratio between 1 : 2 to 1 : 8 were carried out at an initial pH of 7.0 for Cr^{III} , 7.0 for Fe^{III} and 10.0 for Ni^{II} with 3 h equilibration time. The results (Fig. 1b) indicate that an increase in K_d values as aqueous phase to exchanger ratio decrease because increased weight of the sorbent provides more number of active sites for the sorption of metal ions⁶.

The pH investigation of sorption as a function of pH was made at a fixed volume of metal ion solution i.e. 25 ml, 100 mg weight of sorbent and 3 h equilibration time. Fig. 1c gives K_d values for the sorption of Cr^{III} , Fe^{III} and Ni^{II} on SPFP gel at varying pH. It is seen that in general the K_d values decrease with increase in acidity and basicity of the aqueous solution. The reason for low sorption in higher acidic solution is the competition between the excess of H^+ ions in the medium and

Fig. 1b. Effect of weight variation of sorbent on sorption.

positively charged hydrated cationic species present in the solution⁷. For Cr^{III} and Fe^{III} tendency to form hydroxides increases in basic medium. Also there may be a possibility of metal hydroxide colloid formation mainly in case of Fe^{III} and to some extent in Cr^{III} and Ni^{II}. These metal hydroxide colloids may get sorbed on the surface or in the pores, channels and interconnected voids present in the material. The experimental data suggest that SPFP gel has greater potential for Cr^{III}, Fe^{III} and Ni^{II} at pH 7.0, 7.0 and 10.0 respectively at room temperature.

Fig. 1c. Sorption of Cr^{III}, Fe^{III} and Ni^{II} by synthetic analogue of SPFP with varying pH of the solution.

Studies were also carried out at temperatures between 25 to 45 °C. Fig. 1d reveals that uptake of metal ions increases with rise in temperature, indicating better sorption at higher temperature. Better sorption at higher temperature may be either due to acceleration of originally slow sorption steps or due to creation of some new active sites on the sorbent surface. This could also be due to enhanced mobility of metal ions from solution to the sorbent surface. As the equilibria involving sorption of ions, gets agitated due to rise in temperature. Due to thermal agitation, processes like association of ions, aggregation, ion pairing and complex formation may be discouraged in the system⁸. Thus rise in temperature enhances sorption of ions.

Effect of metal ion concentration : It was observed that (Figs. 1c and 1d) sorption of metal ions decreases with increase

in their respective concentration. This can be explained in terms of relatively fewer numbers of active sites at higher metal ion concentration or may be due to decrease in the mobility of metal ions.

Fig. 1d. Effect of temperature on the sorption of Cr^{III}, Fe^{III} and Ni^{II} by synthetic analogue of SPFP.

Conclusion :

An analogue of the mica mineral sodium potassium fluorophlogopite was synthesized hydrothermally. It has been characterized using XRPD, EDS, FT-IR and TGA techniques. The composition of the gel was found to be Na_{0.5}K_{0.5}Mg₃(Si₃AlO₁₀)F₂.6H₂O. The K_d values for Cr^{III}, Fe^{III} and Ni^{II} are higher at low metal ion concentration i.e. 0.01 M. The increase in contact time, weight of sorbent, temperature and pH of the medium show sharp increase in K_d values. It may be proved that the synthesized analogue is a potential candidate for sorption and separation of Cr^{III}, Fe^{III} and Ni^{II} especially for Fe^{III}.

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